

tettix occurrence. Three diseased Jaya tillers were planted in the middle of each plot at 10 DT to serve as initial virus inoculum source.

All insecticide-treated plots showed reduced disease incidence and vector populations. Cypermethrin reduced disease incidence and increased grain yields most effectively (see table). No adults or

nymphs were found in cypermethrin-treated plots. Acephate, FMC 35001, phosphamidon, and demeton-o-methyl sulphoxide were also effective when sprayed on Ratna.

A strong negative correlation between disease incidence and grain yield (-0.614^{**} for Taichung Native 1 and -0.508^{**} for Ratna) indicated that tun-

gro virus disease was the primary cause of reduced yield in the insecticide-treated plots. The positive correlation between disease incidence and leafhopper population ($r = 0.893^{**}$ for Taichung Native 1, and 0.971^{**} for Ratna) shows the disease is spread primarily by *N.*

virescens.

Disease incidence, gain yield, and leafhopper population of insecticide-treated Taichung Native 1 (T) and Ratna (R),^a Cuttack, India.

Treatment	Disease incidence (%)		Grain yield (t/ha)		Leafhoppers (no./20 hills) ^b			
	T	R	T	R	Adults		Nymphs	
					T	R	T	R
Cypermethrin	3.0 a	0.3 a	5.3 a	6.6 a	0.0 a	0.0 a	0.0 a	0.0 a
FMC 35001	50.8 c	3.4 b	1.4 c	5.0 b	33.7 c	13.7 b	0.7 a	1.3 ab
Phosphamidon	56.7 d	6.1 c	1.1 de	4.4 bcd	38.7 cd	14.7 b	1.3 ab	1.0 ab
Demeton-o-methyl sulphoxide	58.1 d	4.5 bc	1.2 cd	4.5 bc	40.0 cd	16.0 bc	6.0 bc	0.0 a
Ofunack	71.5 e	12.5 d	0.9 ef	4.0 cd	42.3 d	18.7 c	8.7 c	0.7 ab
Dichlorvos	73.1 e	11.2 d	0.9 f	3.6 d	46.0 d	23.0 d	33.3 d	2.7 ab
Acephate	31.2 b	2.8 b	1.8 b	5.0 b	22.7 b	15.3 bc	0.7 a	0.7 ab
Control	100.0 f	51.5 e	0.3 g	2.7 e	68.7 e	41.3 e	48.7 e	12.0 c

^aValues followed by a common letter do not differ significantly by Duncan's multiple range test ($P = 0.05$). ^bAv values of 3 replications.

Effect of pruning on rice bacterial blight

A. K. Durra and A. Rafey, Ranchi Agricultural College, Birsa Agricultural University Ranchi, India

At the Ranchi Agricultural College Farm, a brown gora crop with excessive vegetative growth, caused by residual nitrogenous manure, was pruned 50%, 50 days after sowing, to avoid lodging.

Within 2 weeks the pruned crop was severely affected by bacterial blight. Pruned plants had an infection rate of 7 by the Standard Evaluation System for Rice. Adjacent unpruned brown gora had disease severity 3.

Cutting leaves with unsterilized sickles disseminated the pathogen from naturally infected leaves by causing penetration through pruning injury.

Scald susceptibility of cultivars grown at different nitrogen levels

A. K. Misra and S. C. Mathur, Plant Pathology, Division, Central Rice Research Institute (CRRI), Cuttack 753 006, Orissa, India

Incidence of leaf scald caused by *Rhynchosporium oryzae* Hashioka & Yokogi

(= *Gerlachia oryzae* [Hashioka & Yokogi] W. Gams), perfect stage *Monographella albescens* (Thum.) in 25 rice cultivars receiving 50, 100, 150, and 200 kg N/ha was recorded at CRRI farm October–November 1981. IR28 and Pankaj were leaf scald resistant at all nitrogen levels. Eight cultivars were moderately resistant, eight were moderately

susceptible, and seven were susceptible (see table). Susceptibility to leaf scald increased with nitrogen levels. No cultivar was susceptible up to 100 kg N/ha. During the second and third weeks of October, when disease development was maximum, mean minimum temperature was 22.5° C and mean relative humidity was 77%.

Scald susceptibility of 25 rice cultivars grown at different nitrogen levels at CRRI, Cuttack, India.

Cultivar	Disease score ^a (0-9) at given nitrogen level			
	50 kg/ha	100 kg/ha	150 kg/ha	200 kg/ha
	<i>Resistant</i>			
IR28	0	0	0	0
Pankaj	1	1	1	1
	<i>Moderately resistant</i>			
CR294-548-1	0	1	1	3
CR318-549, Jagannath	0	1	3	3
RTN68, IR8	0	3	3	3
CR316-639-1, IR36	1	3	3	3
CR188-10	3	3	3	3
	<i>Moderately susceptible</i>			
CR318-548-7, CR319-644-2	1	3	3	5
CR316-639-2, PR106, Ramkrishna	1	3	5	5
PR107	3	3	5	5
CR318-461, BG90-2	3	5	5	5
	<i>Susceptible</i>			
CR294-548-3	1	1	7	7
CR294-548-2, CR315-621	1	3	7	7
CR294-28-1	1	5	7	7
IR2071-178-3, IET4141	3	5	7	7
Jaya	5	5	7	7

^a1 = resistant, 3 = moderately resistant, 5 = moderately susceptible, 7 = susceptible.